

Teacher Perceptions on the Benefits of a Twelve-Week Storytelling Pedagogical Intervention for Fifth Grade Literacy Instruction in Zambia

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Abstract

Storytelling is a fundamental method of traditional education used to preserve and transmit indigenous knowledge, including skills and tacit knowledge, across generations in traditional Zambia societies. This study investigated primary school teachers' perceptions of the benefits of storytelling-based instructional pedagogy on literacy achievement for fifth-grade students in Nyimba District in Eastern Province of Zambia. Employing a qualitative collective case study design, four fifth-grade teachers were trained to implement a twelve-week storytelling intervention in their classrooms. The participants subsequently underwent structured in-depth post-intervention interviews to gather their perceptions regarding storytelling's impact on literacy among their students. The results supported schema-building and socio-cultural mediation theories, which assert that narrative structures provide a critical framework for literacy instruction, facilitating the integration of new information into existing cognitive models through social interaction. Teachers reported that storytelling offered a holistic, integrated approach to literacy instruction, amplifying foundational skills such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking into a cohesive pedagogical experience. Furthermore, it fostered the development of higher-order cognitive skills and metalinguistic awareness. Storytelling was also noted to promote a collaborative culture, build confidence, and enhance self-expression. The strategy's applicability across subjects, such as integrated science and social science, along with its local cultural relevance, were identified as key components of storytelling pedagogy. Consequently, it can be argued that storytelling represents a cost-effective and culturally adaptable approach that can be scaled across primary schools with targeted teacher training, careful story selection, follow-up tasks, and incorporation into national literacy policies to improve low literacy rates in Zambia.

Keywords: *storytelling, pedagogy, culture, reading, literacy.*

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Introduction

Literacy is widely recognised as a cornerstone of individual empowerment, social inclusion, and economic development worldwide (Banda & Kaani, 2025a; Joshi et al., 2023; Kaani, 2019). UNESCO (2023) argues that contemporary literacy extends beyond basic decoding and writing skills to include digital and media literacy, as well as competencies required for sustainable development, global citizenship, and lifelong learning. Despite this global recognition, millions of children continue to face significant barriers to

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acquiring foundational literacy skills, particularly bilingual learners and those taught through pedagogical approaches misaligned with their cultural and linguistic contexts (Kaani et al., 2016; Serpell, 2023). In many developing countries, including Zambia, Western formal education remains relatively recent and culturally distant, resulting in the marginalisation of culturally responsive literacy strategies rooted in indigenous oral traditions such as storytelling, folktales, and proverbs, despite their demonstrated pedagogical potential (Banda & Kaani, 2025b).

Although literacy is widely acknowledged as central to national development, Zambia continues to experience persistent challenges in improving literacy outcomes among school-going children (Kaani, 2021; Ministry of Education, 2023; Mofu et al., 2023; Moyo & Mwanza, 2025). Regionally, nearly 90% of children in sub-Saharan Africa are unable to read with comprehension by the age of ten, highlighting a widespread learning crisis (African Union, 2024; Banda & Kaani, 2025b). Globally, over 100 million young people remain illiterate, with sub-Saharan Africa disproportionately affected (UNESCO, 2023). In Zambia, literacy deficits are exacerbated by socio-economic inequalities, limited instructional resources, and inadequate teacher preparation (Mofu et al., 2023; Mwanza, 2020). While policy interventions such as the Primary Reading Programme (Tambulukani, 2015), the Primary Literacy Programme (Ministry of Education, 2013), and the 2023 Zambia Education Curriculum Framework (Ministry of Education, 2023) have been implemented, progress has remained slow. Many learners continue to struggle with reading fluency, comprehension, and writing skills (Banda & Kaani, 2025a; Kaani, 2021; Serenje, 2024), underscoring the need for innovative, culturally grounded literacy approaches that are responsive to Zambia's educational realities.

Literature Review

Amid persistent literacy challenges in Zambia, pedagogical innovation has become imperative for improving learners' literacy outcomes (Nyimbili, 2021). One such innovation is narrative storytelling, which has emerged as a highly effective instructional strategy for enhancing learner engagement, vocabulary development, reading comprehension, critical thinking, creativity, and communicative competence (Banda & Kaani, 2025b). Empirical evidence from diverse educational contexts including Nigeria, Korea, Malaysia, and Indonesia demonstrates that storytelling supports deeper language learning and sustained learner motivation, particularly in resource-constrained environments (Dickinson et al., 2012; Irena et al., 2020; Maureen et al., 2022; Miller & Pennycuff, 2008; Satriani, 2021).

In the Zambian context, emerging scholarship highlights storytelling's potential to facilitate intergenerational knowledge transmission while offering a learner-centred alternative to teacher-dominated, rote-based instruction (Banda & Kaani, 2025a; Kaani & Machila, 2022). Although Zambia's curriculum frameworks (Ministry of Education, 2013; 2023) acknowledge the importance of integrating indigenous knowledge and learner-centred methodologies, storytelling remains marginalised in classroom practice, particularly in upper primary grades (Banda & Kaani, 2025b). Traditional Zambian narratives such as folktales, myths, legends, fables, proverbs, riddles, and moral tales provide linguistically rich and cognitively stimulating input for learners. These narratives expose learners to varied vocabulary, complex sentence structures, figurative language, and expressive discourse, thereby strengthening oral language foundations that are critical for literacy development (Kaani & Machila, 2022; Ministry of Education, 2013). Furthermore, clear narrative structures support learners' understanding of sequencing, causality, and plot development, which are essential components of reading comprehension. Compared to decontextualised drills, storytelling enhances motivation and reduces learner disengagement by appealing to imagination and lived experience (Banda & Kaani, 2025b). It also validates learners' cultural identities and promotes ethical reasoning through engagement with moral dilemmas, fostering empathy and critical reflection (Banda & Kaani, 2025a).

Globally, research consistently demonstrates the superiority of narrative storytelling over traditional instructional approaches in improving reading comprehension, particularly among low-proficiency learners. In the United States, Isbell et al. (2004) found that oral storytelling produced stronger

comprehension outcomes than storybook reading among preschool learners, while Wasik and Bond (2001) showed that interactive storytelling significantly enhanced language development. These findings support the notion that storytelling develops learners' "sense of story," enabling deeper meaning-making and higher-order thinking (Miller & Pennycuff, 2008; Morrow & Gambrell, 2011). In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) context, storytelling has been shown to enhance comprehension through increased engagement, schema activation, and contextualised language exposure. Studies from Afghanistan (Sahibzada et al., 2020), Saudi Arabia (Al-Mansour & Al-Shorman, 2011), Iran (Ahmadian & Pashangzadeh, 2013), and Malaysia (Mokhtar et al., 2011) demonstrate significant gains in learners' reading comprehension when storytelling is systematically integrated into instruction. Similarly, Indonesian research across elementary and secondary levels reports improvements in comprehension, motivation, classroom participation, and critical thinking (Kurniawan et al., 2024; Santoso et al., 2023; Sinamo et al., 2023; Wijayanti, 2011; Yulianawati et al., 2022). In Taiwan, integrated storytelling approaches combining oral narration with visual supports benefited both low-proficiency sixth-grade learners and early childhood learners (Huang, 2006; Zheng et al., 2025). In Nigeria, storytelling enhanced learners' comprehension and production in indigenous languages, such as Igbo, highlighting its applicability in multilingual contexts (Nwigwe, 2021). Collectively, these studies indicate that storytelling leverages emotional engagement, interaction, and familiar narrative structures to support meaning construction.

While international evidence strongly supports the effectiveness of storytelling, research from sub-Saharan Africa particularly Zambia remains limited, especially at the upper primary level (Mandyata et al., 2024). In rural districts such as Nyimba, learners face compounded challenges including multilingualism, limited instructional materials, absenteeism, overcrowded classrooms, and difficulties transitioning to English as the language of instruction (Banda & Kaani, 2025b). Narrative storytelling, through practices such as teacher narration, guided questioning, retelling, performance, and the use of cultural artefacts, offers a culturally responsive approach to addressing these challenges.

Storytelling has also been shown to significantly enhance vocabulary development by embedding new words within meaningful contexts, thereby outperforming isolated vocabulary drills (Santoso et al., 2023). Empirical evidence from Germany (Vaahtoranta et al., 2018), the United States (Beck et al., 2013; Biemiller & Boote, 2021), Japan (Uchiyama, 2011), Taiwan (Gao et al., 2020), and Indonesia (Cajuizi & Mandarani, 2025) demonstrates that both explicit and elaborative storytelling approaches yield substantial vocabulary gains. Strong vocabulary knowledge, in turn, supports decoding, inference-making, reading fluency, and overall comprehension, reducing cycles of frustration and disengagement (Bežilová, 2019; Mete et al., 2023; Susanto, 2016).

In terms of reading fluency, storytelling fosters accurate pronunciation, appropriate intonation, and expressive reading within low-anxiety learning environments (Miller & Pennycuff, 2008; Wright, 2008). Studies from Brazil (Lucarevski, 2018), Algeria (Ghounane, 2021), and Japan (Uchiyama, 2011) report notable improvements in oral fluency following storytelling-based instruction. Activities such as retelling, dramatization, and choral narration capitalise on learners' oral strengths and support the transition from familiar oral discourse to formal English literacy.

Storytelling further contributes to writing development by modelling narrative organisation, coherence, and text structure, areas in which many learners experience persistent difficulty (Cragg & Nation, 2007). Indonesian studies demonstrate that storytelling-based interventions effectively bridge oral and written language through interactive planning, retelling, and transcription, resulting in improved coherence, creativity, and written performance (Damayanti, 2016). Additionally, storytelling nurtures creativity and imagination, key components of higher-order literacy by encouraging learners to reconstruct, adapt, and perform narratives (Satriani, 2019; Wright, 2008).

Beyond cognitive and linguistic outcomes, storytelling supports learners' social-emotional development, enhancing confidence, empathy, collaboration, and intrinsic motivation (Bolkan, 2020; Deci & Ryan, 2017; Denham et al., 2021; Gillam et al., 2023; Miller & Pennycuff, 2008). These affective benefits are particularly salient in classrooms characterised by linguistic diversity and limited resources. Therefore, the

effectiveness of storytelling in literacy instruction is grounded in established theoretical frameworks. Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory conceptualises learning as a socially mediated process, with language functioning as a primary cultural tool. Storytelling creates collaborative learning spaces within learners' zones of proximal development, enabling scaffolded participation and the co-construction of meaning. Complementing this perspective, Bruner's (1991) theory of narrative cognition posits that humans are inherently predisposed to organise and remember experiences in narrative form, rendering storytelling a powerful medium for teaching language structures, vocabulary, and comprehension.

Despite substantial international evidence, Zambian research on storytelling remains sparse, particularly in contexts dominated by rote instruction and educational vulnerability (Banda & Kaani, 2025b; Mwanza, 2020; Serenje, 2024). Culturally responsive pedagogy emphasises the importance of integrating learners' cultural experiences to foster identity, engagement, and Singh & Alshammari, 2024). While Zambian folktales and oral traditions offer rich pedagogical potential, empirical validation of storytelling-based literacy instruction especially in rural districts such as Nyimba and in transitional grades like Grade Five is notably lacking. Therefore, the limited body of localised empirical research underscores the need for targeted studies to inform policy and practice, including the National Literacy Framework (Ministry of Education, 2013), and to establish storytelling as a transformative pedagogy for upper primary literacy development in Zambia.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a Qualitative Collective Case Study Design (Stake, 1995; Yin, 2018) to assess the efficacy of a structured storytelling pedagogy intervention for literacy instruction at fifth-grade level. The multiple-case study approach was chosen to yield a nuanced understanding of teachers' perceptions and implementations of the pedagogy across four distinct classroom environments following a twelve-week intervention. This design is optimal for capturing the complexities of real-world educational interventions and addressing the *how* and *why* questions related to perceived outcomes and practical integration.

Participant

Four fifth-grade teachers were purposively sampled from four primary schools in Nyimba district (Patton, 2015) to serve as individual, bounded cases. The following inclusion criteria ensured that participant recruitment would provide rich information: all participants were teaching at the fifth-grade level, had no prior formal training in storytelling pedagogy, and were willing to implement a storytelling approach to literacy. Participants were recruited from four schools within Nyimba district to provide demographic variation while controlling for broader curricular policies. All participants were female, with teaching experience ranging from five to fifteen years.

The Intervention

Before the study commenced, all four teachers took part in a two-day training workshop focused on storytelling pedagogy, exploring its theoretical foundations. The training included Vygotsky's sociocultural theory (Vygotsky, 1978), Bruner's narrative construction of reality (Bruner, 1991), and their practical applications for storytelling. The teachers were trained in specific techniques, such as using vocal variation, props, visual aids, and dialogic questioning, to enhance narrative comprehension and student engagement. After the workshop, they integrated storytelling-based instruction as a core element of their daily literacy block for a duration of twelve weeks. While they received a structured resource kit, they were also encouraged to adapt the strategies to suit their individual classroom contexts.

Data Collection

Data were collected subsequent to the twelve-week intervention period to capture teachers' evolved perceptions regarding the benefits they observed. Data collection involved triangulation from multiple sources to enhance credibility (Patton, 2015). A single 40-minute in-depth semi-structured interview was

conducted with each teacher at the end of the twelve-week storytelling intervention. The interview protocol was designed to elicit rich descriptions of their post-intervention experiences, focusing on the perceived benefits for student learning.

Data Analysis

The data analysis was carried out using a systematic two-phase approach in line with multiple-case study methodology (Yin, 2018). Firstly, the *within-case analysis involved* analysing each teacher's interview transcript individually. Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis, which incorporates open and axial coding, was applied to uncover key themes within each unique context. This method ensured a comprehensive understanding of each teacher's narrative before any comparisons were made. Secondly, the *cross-case analysis was conducted after* the individual case analyses, employing a constant comparative method to identify patterns, commonalities, and divergences across all four cases (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). The aim of this cross-case synthesis was to distil the core benefits and shared experiences of implementing storytelling pedagogy over an extended period, transitioning from individual cases to broader analytical conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was sought and obtained from the University of Zambia Research Ethics Board. Written informed consent was secured from all participants. To ensure confidentiality, all names of individuals, schools, and classes involved were replaced with pseudonyms. The data were stored on a secure, encrypted server.

Results

The implementation of a storytelling-based pedagogical approach produced significant and varied benefits for literacy instruction. The results obtained from teacher interviews and direct classroom observations conducted during the twelve-week intervention period, are organised into seven emergent themes that highlight a profound impact on both foundational skills and higher-order cognitive, and social development.

Holistic Literacy Integration

The first theme identified in the analysis is that the storytelling pedagogical approach facilitates holistic literacy integration in literacy instruction. This method effectively combines the four core literacy skills of reading, writing, listening, and speaking into a single, cohesive pedagogical and learning experience. This "four-in-one" approach offers a meaningful narrative context for learners, moving beyond traditional strategies that tend to isolate the acquisition of skills through separate drills. As noted by Teacher 1:

All basic literacy skills were covered during storytelling time. These included reading, writing, speaking, and listening. When telling a story, we expect the learners to listen. At the end of the story, or when the teacher tells it in parts or segments, there will be comprehension questions. In their responses, the teacher measures listening skills and attention... From the same story, the teacher identifies difficult words (vocabulary), which are read through choral reading to promote correct pronunciation, speed, and word recall. Learners are then asked to write the meanings of words using dictionaries. This enhances reading and writing skills.

The process offers a systematic, sequential, and purposeful approach to instruction, wherein listening functions as the foundational entry point, while speaking is cultivated through comprehension questions and subsequent discussions and debates. Reading skills are enhanced through choral reading and vocabulary activities, whilst writing proficiency is reinforced through meaning construction and independent narrative composition.

Foundational Skill Amplification

The second theme emerging from the data analysis is the amplification of foundational skills. Participants indicated that explicit instruction in foundational mechanics is effectively integrated within the engaging contexts of storytelling, whether narrated by teachers or learners. This approach significantly enhances literacy skills, particularly in learners' handwriting, spelling, and reading fluency. Teacher 2 argued that:

... storytelling enhanced the handwriting of the learners. For example, when sounds were extracted from some words in the story, I demonstrated the handwriting to the learners, following the rules of correct letter formation in cursive writing since they were older learners. Then learners demonstrated in their books, following the letter patterns. The improvement was seen after the storytelling intervention.

She observed these enhancements in learners' letter formation skills for practice words derived from the narrative. The educator also asserted that this approach facilitates the connection between phonics and practical application, stating:

Learners were able to examine the spellings by encoding sounds in written words and decoding words while recognising sound patterns.

Moreover, reading fluency can be cultivated through what participating educators referred to as *choral and repetitive reading*, a methodology that emphasises *correct pronunciation* and consequently leads to effortless recall of words, thereby enabling learners to *read with fluency*.

Cultivation of Higher-Order Cognitive Skills

The two educators further observed that the storytelling framework serves as an effective mechanism for fostering critical thinking and analytical skills. The incorporation of predictive and evaluative comprehension questions encouraged learners to move beyond mere rote memorisation. Teacher 1 remarked that observer-implemented questions such as, *how do you think the story ended? What might have occurred subsequent to this scenario? How could you resolve such a puzzle if it were you?* compel students to analyse and synthesise narrative content from the stories. Furthermore, independent learning activities (ILAs) that require students to undertake their own research and compose stories on guided topics introduced essential *skimming and scanning skills in comprehension passages* and promoted the development of emerging research skills through consultations with teachers, thereby enhancing critical thinking.

Development of Metalinguistic Awareness

Results have also demonstrated that storytelling-based pedagogy ensured that grammar and language conventions were taught organically as tools for effective communication rather than as abstract rules, as observed in conventional teaching practices. The daily story writing activities were instrumental in this development, as learners actively engaged with language structure to render their narratives coherent. One of the participating teachers noted:

The other aspect I observed, which was so important while employing this storytelling strategy, was the utilisation of daily story writing activities. These were independent learning activities (ILAs) assigned to learners aimed at enhancing handwriting, grammar, and correct sentence construction. ...daily story writing activities improved the art of sequencing events, utilising verbs, adverbs, prepositions, nouns, pronouns, adjectives, homophones, punctuation, spelling, handwriting, paragraphing, capital letters, headings to a story, salutations, etc.

The interactive nature of the storytelling method also facilitates *on-the-spot correction* of speech, rendering the learning of grammatical rules immediate and contextual. Consequently, assessment becomes more dynamic rather than static, allowing educators to evaluate both students and teaching methodologies.

Fostering a Collaborative Culture

The methodology fundamentally transforms the classroom dynamic into a more collaborative and inclusive learning culture. This change allows educators to break down traditional barriers by actively involving pupils and community members as partners in storytelling activities. Tasks were specifically designed to engage community members in storytelling within the classroom and in researching narratives

from guardians or peers, fostering a *supportive* ecosystem for literacy. The peer-to-peer and community consultation model encouraged learning through *discussions, consultations, and critical* thinking, creating vibrant local communities of practice that extended beyond the classroom.

Building Confidence and Self-Expression

Another critical outcome of this study is the observable growth in learner confidence and identity. The secure, narrative space established through the camaraderie of storytelling provides a platform for learners to discover their own voices. According to one respondent, permitting learners to debate the contents of each story "enhanced oral literacy and grammar" and fostered self-assurance. It was particularly evident that learners began to take ownership of their new language skills, as they articulated:

I observed that this methodology allowed learners to explain and debate issues at hand and from the story. This further enhanced oral literacy and grammar. They began to utilise more of the sentences and language extracted from classroom stories in their daily conversations with peers, teachers, and the community.

The transition from passive recipients and consumers of literacy learning materials to active and confident users of language constitutes a cornerstone of authentic literacy development.

Cross-Curricular Application and Relevance

Finally, the effectiveness of storytelling pedagogy proved to be versatile able to accommodate a wide range of competent levels among learners, which extended its benefits beyond the literacy lesson to the entire school curriculum. The strategy demonstrated that *storytelling was integrated in all the subjects*, with learners writing their own stories on topics like *organic and inorganic fertilizers*. This approach *made the teaching of science easy* and demonstrates the role of literacy as a tool for learning. Ultimately, the approach empowered students to become active agents in their own education. As one teacher conclusively stated,

Storytelling is integrated in all the subjects. For instance, I gave the learners to write on "organic and inorganic fertilizers... This strategy is too nice as it makes the work of the teacher easy as most of the tasks were done by the learners themselves enriching in content covered in various subjects.

The communal nature of oral storytelling promotes a collaborative culture and builds confidence and self-expression by valuing local knowledge and voices. It also highlights cross-curricular relevance by linking narratives to history, civic education, and environmental science, thereby creating a truly decolonised and empowering learning environment.

Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that storytelling transcends its role as a mere instructional technique, emerging instead as a culturally relevant catalyst for holistic literacy development. Thematic analysis revealed strong consensus among teachers regarding its effectiveness in addressing foundational literacy deficits, with observable improvements across all four language modalities. Specifically, learners demonstrated enhanced reading comprehension and inferential skills, increased writing creativity, coherence, grammatical accuracy, and clarity, improved listening attention, retention, and responsiveness, and greater speaking fluency, vocabulary use, and confidence with reduced hesitation. Teachers attributed these gains to the inherently motivating, interactive nature of storytelling, which fosters a low-anxiety, high-engagement environment and provides repeated exposure to rich linguistic models within meaningful contexts. These outcomes align with international research demonstrating storytelling's efficacy in strengthening reading comprehension (Dickinson et al., 2012; Morrow, 2009), writing fluency and coherence (Maureen et al., 2021; Morrow, 2009), vocabulary acquisition (Barwasser et al., 2021; Mokhtar et al., 2011), and oral proficiency (Chikamadu et al., 2022; Khodabandeh, 2018), particularly in second-language and resource-constrained contexts.

The intervention also produced substantial improvements in learners' handwriting, particularly in cursive fluency, legibility, and consistency of letter formation. Teachers modelled correct stroke sequences for phonically regular words derived from narratives and provided guided tracing, copying, and free-writing

extensions. This contextualized, multisensory approach contrasts sharply with isolated handwriting drills and yielded gains described by teachers as “surprising and rapid,” even among learners previously producing barely legible script. These findings challenge the widely held assumption that handwriting deficits in late-primary grades are intractable. They align with phase-theory models of literacy acquisition (Ehri & McCormick, 1998; Ehri, 2014), which suggest that embedding orthographic-motor practice within meaningful linguistic contexts accelerates the consolidation of letter-sound-motor associations. Neuroimaging research further corroborates these findings, showing that contextualized handwriting engages broader reading networks compared to decontextualized copying (James & Engelhardt, 2012).

Storytelling also effectively integrated cognitive and metalinguistic skills, fostering higher-order thinking often overlooked in conventional literacy instruction. Observations and teacher reports indicated that learners regularly engaged in prediction, inference, and critical analysis of characters, events, and plot developments. This supports Bruner’s (1991) assertion that narratives provide a powerful scaffold for higher-order cognition. The early development of these skills is critical for long-term academic success, underpinning advanced comprehension, disciplinary thinking, and performance in summative assessments. Additionally, learners demonstrated enhanced metalinguistic awareness by reflecting explicitly on language use, identifying figurative expressions, and evaluating word choice, a key predictor of literacy proficiency that is frequently neglected in traditional instruction. These findings align with meta-analytic evidence showing that inferential questioning within narrative-based instruction yields greater gains in deep comprehension than conventional skills-focused approaches (Nagy & Townsend, 2012; Singh & Alshammari, 2024). Cognitive research further suggests that storytelling activates schema networks, strengthens connections between prior knowledge and new information, and enhances attention and memory through emotional engagement (Haven, 2014). In multilingual and resource-limited contexts, storytelling offers a culturally grounded mechanism for bridging surface-level decoding and higher-order comprehension.

The intervention also fostered learners’ cultural identity, confidence, and self-expression. Increased participation among previously reticent learners suggests that storytelling promotes a sense of ownership, security, and self-efficacy. The use of folktales, proverbs, and culturally familiar narratives enabled learners to express themselves freely, reduce anxiety, and take academic risks. This culturally responsive approach aligns with recommendations to integrate local knowledge into pedagogy to enhance learner confidence, expression, and educational quality (Kaani & Machila, 2022; Ministry of Education, 2023). Furthermore, storytelling transformed classroom dynamics, shifting interaction from teacher-dominated talk to collaborative meaning-making. Learners co-constructed narratives through shared ideas, feedback, and discussion, reflecting indigenous African learning traditions that emphasize communal participation and knowledge sharing. This bi-directional pedagogical model strengthened oral literacy, emotional development, and public communication skills, supporting prior research on the role of shared reading and storytelling in fostering confidence and self-expression (Holdaway, 1979).

The study further revealed improvements in learners’ skimming and scanning strategies, critical for navigating informational texts and meeting academic demands beyond primary grades. Storytelling tasks that required identifying key events, sequence markers, character information, and textual evidence naturally embedded these skills. Learners who had previously relied on slow, word-by-word reading demonstrated more efficient and purposeful engagement with both familiar and unfamiliar texts. This aligns with evidence from Indonesia showing that embedding reading strategies within interactive, meaning-driven activities yields greater gains than isolated instruction (Basuki, 2018; Sari, 2024). These results underscore that strategic reading is most effectively developed when embedded in authentic, engaging tasks rather than taught in decontextualized settings.

Finally, storytelling enriched learners’ content knowledge and promoted authentic interdisciplinary connections. Teachers selected narratives embedding key concepts from social studies, science, and health education, extending learning through discussion, dramatization, and guided writing. Learners spontaneously transferred story-based knowledge to other subjects, reflecting “learning without noticing they are learning.” This supports international research demonstrating storytelling’s cross-curricular

effectiveness in enhancing conceptual understanding and engagement (Cheeseman & Gapp, 2014; O'Neill & Beattie, 2020). By anchoring abstract concepts in vivid, memorable narratives, storytelling renders complex ideas concrete and personally relevant while promoting active processing and knowledge application.

In sum, storytelling emerges as a highly effective and culturally grounded pedagogical approach that simultaneously strengthens foundational literacy, higher-order cognitive and metalinguistic skills, learner confidence, and cross-curricular understanding. It represents a low-cost, scalable, and contextually relevant strategy capable of transforming literacy instruction in Zambia and similar resource-constrained, multilingual settings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that storytelling-based pedagogy transcends conventional methods, serving as a culturally grounded catalyst for holistic literacy development in Zambian primary classrooms. It enhances foundational skills in reading, writing, listening, speaking, and handwriting, while fostering higher-order thinking, metalinguistic awareness, strategic reading, cultural identity, self-efficacy, collaboration, and interdisciplinary learning. By leveraging Zambia's oral traditions, storytelling addresses persistent literacy deficits within multilingual, resource-constrained settings. Its low-cost, adaptable, and scalable nature underscores its transformative potential, supporting curricular integration, targeted teacher training, and further research to advance educational equity and literacy outcomes across sub-Saharan African contexts.

Limitations

The study's reliance on a small sample of only four teachers from schools in Nyimba District limits the transferability of findings to broader Zambian contexts or diverse primary settings.

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Declaration of Conflict of Interest

We declare no potential conflict of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

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